

USEFULNESS OF TECHNOLOGICAL ASSISTED TEXTBOOK AS LEARNING RESOURCE IN THE TEACHING LEARNING PROCESS

Mrs. Smita Santosh Mhatre

Research Scholar

University of Mumbai

Research Guide: Dr. Frances Ketan Vaidya

Abstract

The pandemic situation has caused shutting down of schools, colleges and other educational institutions globally. More than a billion students are not able to avail the classroom boons. Ergo, education has drastically modified giving an uplift to e-Learning through the utility of digital platforms. Analysis on how the education sector responds to this pandemic, making the maximum and optimistic use of digital platforms how government and SCERT brought the Diksha app in use making education easily available for teachers, students and parents. Education must always be based on the recent situation or scenario. Education should be oriented to the present situation and not to past. Time changes and so the scenario. We need to learn and understand the new techniques to study. Learning is the act of acquiring or modified and reinforcing existing, behaviours, skills, values, or preferences which may lead to potential changes in synthesizing information, depth of the knowledge, attitude or behaviour related to the type and range of experience.

Key Words:- *e-Learning, techniques, digital platforms.*

Introduction:

“Technology will not replace great teachers but technology in the hands of great teachers can be transformational!” George Couros

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this pandemic, making the maximum and optimistic use of digital platforms how government and SCERT brought the Diksha app in use making education easily available for teachers, students and parents.

Time changes and so does the scenario. As the time changed audio-visual material came ahead. It was in the form of OHP, cassettes, songs small clips. Over the time this too has changed. The materials provided from government were now in the form of knowledge - based material. So that the students could learn in their own speed and capacity. With the help of this knowledge-based material teacher could involve every student in activity.

Technology in textbook: Formal education is given by specially qualified teachers. Teachers use various methods like lecture, discussion, demonstration, role plays, team teaching while teaching in class room. Teachers need to enhance their teaching skills by using innovative teaching strategies with the help of effective learning resources. The use of this material was started in the form of small cards, pictures, letters and tables. In recent advances new changes have taken place in education material.

The audio materials are now replaced by audio-visual tools. Educational materials were available in the form of Cassette and Cd. Moreover there are online classes provided to make education or studying easy in the forms of apps and online tutors. Technology has taken a strong leap in different sectors. We can see step vies growth of technology. Education sectors are not far from this progress. Studies have changed a lot in terms of teaching methods. We look forward to the positive changes in education as per the need of hour. Early learning methods were teacher centric and later it becomes a student centric.

Initiative of State Government:

The state government of Maharashtra had put forward the introduction of e content with QR code in diksha app (Digital infrastructure for knowledge sharing) and was executed in the year 2019. With a technical support and backup of EkStep. With the main objective of making textbook material available for students and teachers on a digital platform using QR code. It covered all mediums (English, Hindi, Marathi, Urdu, Telegu, Malayalam etc.) all standards (1-10) and all subjects. Approximately 13,600 QR codes are to be put in place with virtue of 586 teachers which was initiated in Maharashtra.

Need of Study:

In this research, researcher is studying about the technological assisted QR coded text book. This research has two main functions. The first thing about it is the technical and

the other thing is related to the study. Electronic educational materials are produced with the help of the of technology and they have been printed in textbook for the first time through the print code. However through this research it has been studied the uses of QR coded textbook. Expectations of parents from QR code and e-Content.

Title of Study:

“Usefulness of Technological Assisted Textbook as learning resource in the Teaching Learning process.

Research Statements:-

- i. Does the QR coded e-content is helpful in the teaching learning?
- ii. Does the QR Coded e-content is a better option than any other teaching learning resource?
- iii. Is it beneficial for self-study?
- iv. Is it effective for self-learning of all the subjects?
- v. Is DIKSHA APP, a useful App in teaching learning process?
- vi. Does it make the teaching learning process more interesting?
- vii. Does it help to understand the difficult concepts better?
- viii. Does it help to user to get deeper insight of the concept?
- ix. Does it provide instant feedback?
- x. Does it give enriched material?

Aim of Study: -

To study the usefulness of technological of assisted (QR Coded) textbook as a learning resource.

Objectives of the Study:

- i. To study the usefulness of technological assisted (QR coded) text books for parents.
- ii. To find out the percentage of parents for usefulness of technological assisted (QR coded) text books.

Methodology of the Study

Methodology:-Descriptive Survey Method

Sampling Technique: - Purposive random sampling. This research consists of 240 parents of NMMC schools, Govt aided schools and Unaided schools.

Researcher will check the opinion of parents to collect data,

Limitations of the study: -

The researcher has included parents of Government school, aided school and unaided

schools of state board from Navi Mumbai.

Tools used for data collection.-

For the purpose of present study, the researcher will use tool to collect information from parents of students of N.M.M.C, aided and unaided schools. These include readymade and researcher made tools.

A. Researcher made tool. Questionnaires for parents opinion, about technological assisted text book in teaching process.

C. Personal data sheet of parents was prepared by the researcher.

Techniques Of Data Analysis

Data collection is very important for analysis. With the help of collected data .The analysis and interpretation of data involves the objectives material in the possession of the researcher and his subjective reactions. The value of standard deviation will be used to measure the opinion of teachers as well as students. Correlation will be checked among variables.

Data analysis-Researcher will use the following techniques. The data is necessary for descriptive analysis of hypothesis. Certain descriptive statistics will be used in order to describe the nature and distribution of the scores obtained on the various tests.

Scoring

Sr No	STATEMENTS	YES	NO
1.	Does the QR coded e-content is helpful in the teaching learning process?	89%	11%
2.	Does the QR Coded e-content is a better option than any other teaching learning resource?	79%	21%
3.	Is it not beneficial for self-study?	73%	27%
4.	Is it effective for self-learning of all the subjects?	82%	18%
5.	Is DIKSHA APP, a useful App in teaching learning process?	71%	29%
6.	Does it make the teaching learning process more interesting?	83%	17%
7.	Does it help to understand the difficult concepts better?	86%	14%
8.	Does it help the user to get deeper insight to the concept?	87%	13%
9.	Does it provide instant feedback?	66%	34%
10.	Does it give enriched material?	73%	27%

Findings: -

From the above table it can be concluded that 213 parents are agree with the first statement i.e “Does the QR coded e-content is helpful in the teaching learning process?” whereas 27 parents think that the QR coded e-content is not helpful.

In second statement 190 parents are agree that the QR Coded e-content is a better option than any other teaching learning resource, whereas 50 parents think that the QR Coded e-content is not a better option than any other teaching learning resource.

In third statement 176 parents are agree that QR Coded e-content beneficial for self-study whereas 64 parents think that QR Coded e-content is not beneficial for self-study.

In fourth statement 197 parents are agree that it is effective for self-learning of all the subjects whereas 43 parents think that QR Coded e-content is not effective for self-learning of all the subjects.

In fifth statement 170 parents are agree that DIKSHA APP is a useful App in teaching learning process whereas 70 parents think that DIKSHA APP is not a useful App in teaching learning process.

In sixth statement 198 parents are agree that QR Coded e-content makes the teaching learning process more interesting whereas 42 parents think that QR Coded e-content does not make teaching learning process more interesting.

In seventh statement 206 parents are agree that QR Coded e-content helps to understand the difficult concepts better whereas 34 parents think that QR Coded e-content does not help to understand the difficult concepts.

In eighth statement 209 parents are agree that QR Coded e-content helps the user to get deeper insight to the concept whereas 31 parents think that it does not help the user to get deeper insight to the concept.

In ninth statement 159 parents are agree that QR Coded e-content helps to provide instant feedback whereas 81 parents think that it does not help to provide instant feedback.

In tenth statement 197 parents are agree that QR Coded e-content gives enriched material whereas 43 parents think that it does not give enriched material.

The majority of parents are aware about the QR Codes which are attached to the textbook, and they find it useful for students in study. But some parents find that it is not useful for students.

Conclusion- For the current survey, researcher concluded that 80% of parents think that QR Coded e-content is useful for students in study where as 20% of parents think that it is not good learning resource in teaching learning process and also not useful for self-study.

Suggestions:- If 20% of parents find that this QR coded textbooks are not useful, it means they might be not familiar with digital device or they are not aware of it. So School principals should conduct training program for the awareness of QR coded. It is necessary to train parents.

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